

THE SOURCES OF THE MYSTICISM(SUFI) DOCTRINE

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Annotation: the article talks about the source basis of the science of Sufism along with the science of Islamic religion - the science of Sharia, the science of aqeedah (donation).

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The word "Deen" means "reckoning", "punishment", "reward" from the Arabic language [1:135]. And the word "Ilm" from the Arabic language means "a sign that distinguishes one thing from another" [2:29]. "Iqra" in the command of Islam means "Read!", "Recite!" started with words meaning. There is a great meaning in the fact that its divine miracle is called "Qur'an", i.e. "reading" or "reading", it means that "This religion is a religion based on knowledge and enlightenment, this Word is a Word based on knowledge and enlightenment" [3:48]

The religion of Islam consists of 3 great sciences, the first of which is the science of Aqeed, the second is the science of Shariat, and the third is the science of charity.

Imam Ghazali said in his famous book "Ikhyou Ulumid-Deen": "Aqeed" is the knowledge by which monotheism is perceived and the nature and attributes of Allah subhanahu wa ta'ala are known.[4:206]

The word "Aqidah" is derived from the Arabic verb "aqada" which means "to fasten one thing to another." Islamic creed is a complex of beliefs that binds a Muslim person to certain verses. When a certain knowledge becomes a belief that guides our thoughts, emotions and actions. Therefore, belief must be based on

knowledge.[5:10]

The word Shari'at is an Arabic word that means a threshold and a place to drink water, the right path, Islamic rulings, legal rules of law, a complex of practical rulings introduced and formed on the basis of the Word of God, the Islamic legal system.

"...Shari'at is a set of norms and instructions that must be followed unconditionally, established by Allah and sent to people through our prophet Muhammad (s.a.vq)" - "Law of Allah", "Decision and order of the heavens".[6:567]

"Ehsan"(Donation) is derived from the Arabic word - kindness, sincerity, kindness, gift of something, charity. [6:586]

In the Qur'an, sincerity in fulfilling religious obligations is the opposite of hypocrisy in one of the hadiths quoted from Umar ibn Khattab (RA):

"Ehsan is to pray to God as if you were seeing him. Even if you do not see Him, pray as if He sees you. Ghazali used the term "Ehsan" together with the word "adl-adolat", which together acquired the meaning of "justice and conscience".

The word charity as a dogmatic concept forms a general religious concept along with the concepts of Islam and faith. Here, ihsan means full, unquestioning and unreinterpreted acceptance of all religious beliefs, meaning deep devotion to all its precepts.

The word muhsin, meaning religious, comes from the concept of charity. In daily istilah, the term of charity is ikhlas: it means purity of heart, sincerity in thoughts and actions.

In Sufism, Ihsan is the highest stage of faith, followed by faith and then Islam, which corresponds to the concepts of Sharia-Tariqat-Haqiqat.

Ihsan is usually closely related to the concept of Sufism.

That is, it means spiritual training, purification, good behavior, self-improvement, good morals (etc.). Muhammad (s.a.v.) and the Siddiquis - the Khulafai Rashidin,

the dear servants of God who did not deviate from the path of the first Companions, were frugal, extremely pious, renounced the world, and turned to asceticism - "Sufi", and the path they followed began to be called "Tasawwuf".

Sufism is a beautiful doctrine of Sufism, and its various paths are called "sects" and "leeches". Sufism teaches us to reach the truth of the Qur'an and Sunnah and follow it with all our being.

Sufism is described in the work "Secrets of Sufism" by Muhammad Nurullah Said al-Jazari: "It is a very useful and independent science that reforms the spiritual world of a person, is the most effective for the treatment of broken hearts, and gathers a person around the truths." [7:4]

Sufism explains the meanings of "heart", "soul", "mind" and "nafs" with special care and states how a Muslim servant should treat each of them, and sets out the implementation of that statement.[8:66]

Mashayih and mystics have given various and beautiful definitions to Sufism. Below we describe some of the definitions given in the work of Hazrat Shaykh "Imagination of Sufism".

Sufism is a sect, the purpose of which is to free the heart from other than Allah, to worship the Creator sincerely, and to separate the soul from other than Him to the world of purity. Sufism is a philosophy of life that morally develops the self, which becomes reality through certain practical mathematics and sometimes leads to a sense of immersion in a higher reality. It also leads to enjoyment and intellectual enlightenment.

Sufism is a science that studies the state of the soul - good and bad, the way to purify the bad, the way to adorn the good, the mood of walking towards God and the way of escaping to Him. That is, not seeking refuge from anyone other than Himself .[8:31-32]

Sufism is to love God and to be satisfied in the way of attaining his vassal. Sufism is a science that transcends reason. The science of Sufism is knowledge,

inspiration, and discovery that comes from God. Sufism is familiarity with the unseen world. Sufism is spiritual education.

In conclusion, it can be said that the idea of Sufism is to purify the soul in order to gain the approval of God, and strive to become the owner of good morals, that is, to become moral according to the behavior of Allah and His Messenger. Human perfection can only be achieved through the preservation of the purity of the soul, which depends on taking steps to ensure the victory of the soul over the body.

Islamic Sufism is a path built directly on Islamic principles without any external influences.

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